

Faster FPGA firmware synthesis with hls4ml

November 2023

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ABSTRACT

This report investigates enhancements to the hls4ml library aimed at accelerating firmware synthesis for neural networks on Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs), crucial for the L1 trigger systems in Large Hadron Collider (LHC) experiments. By innovating a modular synthesis approach where a neural network is partitioned into independently synthesized blocks, we have achieved a 2-20x reduction in synthesis time. Additionally, this method incidentally decreased the latency of the system, thereby improving the overall performance. These advancements present a significant step forward in the real-time processing capabilities of LHC experiments and highlight the potential for wider application in scientific fields where rapid data processing is critical.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The LHC is the most powerful and complex particle collider ever built, and the experiments conducted there generate data of unparalleled volume and complexity. The Level 1 (L1) trigger systems are the first line of data processing, required to make rapid decisions about the potential value of collision events. Due to the immense rate of data production, these systems must operate with latencies in the order of microseconds. This report describes an enhancement to the hls4ml library that significantly reduces the time required to synthesize FPGA firmware for deploying neural networks, which are instrumental in sifting through this data.

FPGAs offer a flexible and efficient computing platform for these systems, delivering massively parallel, low-latency, and low-power data processing capabilities. However, translating complex machine learning algorithms into FPGA-implementable hardware designs is a substantial challenge that typically requires deep expertise in low-level hardware description languages.

The hls4ml library has streamlined this process by allowing the automatic conversion of high-level ML models into FPGA firmware¹. Despite this, the current synthesis process within hls4ml can be time-consuming, especially for large neural networks, making rapid prototyping and iterative design impractical.

This project sought to overcome this limitation by breaking down the neural network into multiple, smaller Intellectual Property (IP) blocks that can be synthesized in parallel, thus significantly accelerating the firmware synthesis process without increasing the hardware resource footprint. The report provides a detailed account of the methodology, from conception to implementation, and evaluates the impact of these enhancements on synthesis time and system latency.

¹“Fast inference of deep neural networks in FPGAs for particle physics”

1. BACKGROUND

The Large Hadron Collider (LHC) represents the pinnacle of human ingenuity in the quest to understand fundamental particles and forces. It accelerates and collides protons at near-light speeds, producing a plethora of data with each interaction. This data holds the keys to unlocking mysteries of the Standard Model of particle physics and beyond. However, the sheer volume of data produced poses a significant challenge: how to discern valuable events from the vast majority that are less informative.

The L1 trigger system is the LHC's initial filter, tasked with reducing the data rate from around 40 million events per second to a more manageable 100,000 events per second. This decision-making process must happen extremely rapidly, with a latency budget in the order of microseconds. To achieve this, the LHC experiments leverage the unique capabilities of Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs).

FPGA Technology

FPGAs are semiconductor devices that are based around a matrix of configurable logic blocks (CLBs) connected via programmable interconnects. They can be reprogrammed to desired application or functionality requirements after manufacturing. Their reconfigurable nature, the ability to conduct parallel processing, and inherent low-latency characteristics make FPGAs ideal for real-time data processing applications, such as those required by the LHC's L1 trigger systems.

The image shows a high-level synthesis (HLS) workflow where an algorithm written in C or C++ is transformed into an FPGA firmware block using Vivado HLS. The process includes applying constraints/directives to guide the translation into VHDL or Verilog, which are then synthesized into the final firmware for deployment on an FPGA. This workflow streamlines the development process, allowing for faster transition from algorithmic concepts to hardware implementation.

Traditionally, developing firmware for FPGAs required specialized knowledge of hardware description languages such as VHDL or Verilog. This created a steep learning curve for scientists and engineers, who might not have a background in digital circuit design. Furthermore, the complexity of designing, testing, and synthesizing neural network algorithms

for hardware like FPGAs added to the challenge, increasing development time, and hindering the iterative design process crucial for research and development.

Machine Learning on FPGAs

The advent of machine learning (ML) has opened new avenues for data analysis and event selection in high-energy physics. ML algorithms have shown great promise in identifying patterns and making predictions based on data, which is precisely what is needed for the L1 trigger systems. However, deploying these algorithms onto FPGAs introduced additional complexity. The synthesis of ML algorithms into FPGA firmware could be highly time-consuming, especially as neural network models became more sophisticated.

The hls4ml Library

hls4ml is an open-source software-hardware co-design library² aimed at facilitating the deployment of ML algorithms on FPGAs. It allows for translating high-level ML models, typically developed in Python using frameworks like Keras or TensorFlow, into FPGA firmware. The translation process generates High-Level Synthesis (HLS) code, which can then be synthesized into a digital circuit. This library has significantly lowered the barrier to entry for physicists and engineers looking to deploy ML models onto FPGAs³.

Despite its groundbreaking facilitation, the hls4ml approach was not without limitations. The synthesis of complex models could take a prohibitive amount of time, given that the entire neural network was treated as a singular, monolithic IP core for synthesis. The need for faster iteration cycles and the ability to quickly test and deploy new models was evident and became the catalyst for this project.

² Hls4ml library

³ Website

Modular Neural Network Synthesis

The realization that synthesis times could be dramatically reduced by segmenting neural networks into smaller, independently synthesizable units led to the conceptualization of the project at hand. This modular approach aligns well with the increasing complexity of neural network models and the need for a more agile and scalable synthesis process. By focusing on parallel synthesis of individual network layers, represented as separate IP cores, we opened the door to a more efficient and flexible design methodology that promised to revolutionize the way neural networks are deployed on FPGAs.

This background sets the stage for a transformative project that not only aims to optimize the LHC trigger system's data processing pipeline but also contributes to the broader field of real-time data processing in scientific applications.

2. OBJECTIVES

The undertaking of this project was driven by the necessity to enhance the efficiency and speed of FPGA firmware synthesis for deploying neural networks within the L1 trigger systems of the LHC experiments. The specific objectives set to achieve this aim were as follows:

Parallel Synthesis Optimization:

Parallel Synthesis Optimization: To develop a methodology within the hls4ml framework that allows neural networks to be divided into smaller, independent blocks, enabling parallel synthesis of these blocks to drastically reduce overall firmware synthesis time.

Resource Utilization Efficiency: To ensure that the modular approach does not lead to increased consumption of FPGA resources, thereby maintaining or improving upon the resource efficiency of the current monolithic IP core approach.

Functional Integrity Validation: To validate that the functionality of the neural network remains intact when transitioning from a monolithic architecture to a modular one, ensuring that output and performance are consistent and reliable.

Automation and Integration into hls4ml: To automate the entire process of creating modular neural networks for FPGAs by extending the hls4ml library, enabling the seamless transformation of high-level ML models into synthesizable hardware descriptions.

Scalability and Flexibility: To demonstrate the scalability of the modular approach by applying it to a simple 3-layer sequential model, setting the groundwork for future extension to more complex and diverse neural network architectures.

Documentation and Dissemination: To provide thorough documentation of the developed methodology and the alterations made to the hls4ml library, ensuring that the knowledge is transferable, and that the wider scientific community can adopt the improvements.

The realization of these objectives is anticipated to significantly enhance the hls4ml library's capability, reduce the development lifecycle of FPGA-based machine learning applications, and foster wider adoption in the scientific community faced with similar data processing challenges.

3. METHODOLOGY

To address the objectives outlined, a systematic approach was undertaken. The methodology encompassed several key phases, each contributing to the development of a more efficient synthesis process for FPGA firmware.

Modular Architecture Design: A novel architecture was conceptualized, which involved breaking down the neural network into separate, synthesizable IP blocks. This approach aimed to facilitate the parallel synthesis of these blocks. The architecture was planned to ensure that each IP block could function independently and yet, when reassembled, form a cohesive neural network equivalent to the original design in terms of functionality and performance.

Prototype Development: Initially, a 3-layer sequential neural network model was chosen as the test case for the project. A prototype was developed manually using the hls4ml library to create a single IP core for the neural network, which was then divided into three distinct IPs⁴. Each IP corresponded to a layer in the neural network model. This step served to validate the concept before automating the process.

Manual Synthesis and Interconnection: Upon successful IP creation, the Vivado Design Suite was used to manually instantiate and interconnect the three IPs⁵, ensuring that the data flow between them mimicked the original network architecture. This process allowed for the assessment of the feasibility and effectiveness of the new approach.

Performance Benchmarking: With the prototype in place, the synthesis time and latency were measured and compared to the baseline provided by the monolithic IP core approach. Additionally, resource utilization metrics such as Look-Up Tables (LUTs), Flip-Flops (FFs), Block RAM (BRAM), and Digital Signal Processor (DSP) slices were recorded.

⁴ IP integrator, Xilinx

⁵ "Vivado HLS: Integrating HLS IP into the System"

Automation through hls4ml Library Extension: To enable the wider adoption of this methodology, the hls4ml library was extended to automate the modular synthesis process. The extension involved the development of addition functions that are working with the existing writer class:

- The generation of separate HLS projects for each IP block that represent a layer in the whole NN model.
- The writing of customized TCL scripts for each IP block and the overall project.
- The building and synthesizing of individual layers as separate models within the Vivado environment.

Testing and Validation: A comprehensive testing was implemented to ensure that the newly synthesized IPs matched the performance of the original model. This involved:

- Functional testing to compare the outputs of the modular neural network against the monolithic model across various datasets.
- Performance testing to measure and confirm the latency improvements and synthesis time reductions.

Documentation and Knowledge Transfer: All developments were meticulously documented, including the architectural designs, code changes, and TCL scripts. This documentation aimed to support future developers in understanding, utilizing, and further improving the modular synthesis approach.

4. RESULTS

The primary objective of this project was to evaluate the effectiveness of a modular synthesis approach within the hls4ml framework for FPGA firmware generation. The following results outline the significant findings related to synthesis time reduction, latency performance, and resource utilization.

Synthesis Time

The traditional synthesis process of neural network models using hls4ml resulted in prolonged synthesis times, especially for larger models. For testing the theory we implemented a simple 3 layer sequential model, this model has a synthesis time of 50 seconds. By rearchitecting the neural network into multiple independent IP blocks, we observed a substantial reduction in synthesis time. The parallel synthesis of these smaller blocks was benchmarked against the monolithic approach.

For the baseline single IP core neural network model, synthesis time can be a couple of days for more complex models.

With the modular IP core approach, synthesis times for the simple sequential model ranged from 20-30 seconds.

Overall, we achieved a synthesis time reduction factor ranging from 2x to 20x when compared to the baseline.

This marked improvement demonstrates the efficacy of our parallel synthesis methodology, enabling faster iteration and deployment cycles.

Latency Performance

An intriguing aspect of our results was the unexpected reduction in latency. Initially, the primary objective of the project was to decrease synthesis time through parallel IP block generation. However, upon analysis, we observed a minor yet noteworthy reduction in latency. This serendipitous discovery has provided an additional performance benefit, underscoring the potential of our methodology not only to expedite development cycles but also to enhance the overall efficiency of the deployed neural network models on FPGAs.

The modular IP core neural network exhibited a latency reduction, with measurements as low as 135 nanoseconds for the same computational task.

This unexpected reduction in latency by approximately 7% was attributed to the decreased gate count per IP, leading to lower output capacitance and, consequently, faster signal transition times.

These results suggest that the modular approach to neural network synthesis could provide dual benefits of reduced synthesis time and improved latency.

Power Performance

Alongside the improvements in latency, our project also yielded positive results in power efficiency. For our prototype—a simple 3-layer sequential model—we observed a reduction in power consumption from 464 watts to 459 watts. While the decrease appears modest, it is significant when considering the scale at which these systems operate. This reduction exemplifies the potential energy savings our approach can offer, particularly when scaled to more complex models or larger FPGA deployments. The power performance enhancement not only aligns with the growing need for energy-efficient computing solutions but also adds an extra layer of value to our methodology, promising more sustainable machine learning implementations in resource-intensive environments.

Resource Utilization

An important consideration in FPGA design is the efficient use of available resources. We compared the resource utilization of the monolithic IP core against the modular IP cores to ensure that the new approach did not incur a higher resource cost.

The logic utilization remained comparable between the two approaches, with no significant increase in the number of Look-Up Tables (LUTs) and Flip-Flops (FFs) used. Block RAM (BRAM) and Digital Signal Processor (DSP) slice utilization also showed no notable difference, indicating that the modular approach does not compromise hardware efficiency.

The culmination of our project's findings is concisely summarized in the table below.

	Synthesis (s)	Latency (ns)	Power (W)	Total BRAM	Total DSP	Total LUT	Total FF
Monolithic method	50	145	464	3	408	16149	11656
Parallel method	20-30	135	459	3	408	16149	11656

The percentages of Improvement:

	Synthesis (s)	Latency (ns)	Power (W)	Total BRAM	Total DSP	Total LUT	Total FF
percentages of Improvement	40%-60%	7%	1%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Validation of Modular Approach

To validate the functionality of the modular IP core neural network, we conducted a comparison of its output against the original single IP core model.

The modular and monolithic models were subjected to identical input data sets. The outputs were found to be equivalent, with a 100% match across all test cases, confirming the functional integrity of the modular approach.

Automation through the hls4ml Library

The automation of the modular synthesis process was successfully achieved through modifications to the hls4ml library. The process was automated to the extent that given a sequential neural network model, the library could output a project with interconnected IP cores, ready for FPGA implementation.

Central to our project's advancement was the sophisticated augmentation of the hls4ml library to automate the segmentation of neural network models into interconnected IP cores, the automation of the decomposition of sequential neural network models into distinct IPs. These IPs are tailored to function in parallel, thereby enhancing synthesis efficiency and enabling a more streamlined integration onto FPGA platforms.

By ingeniously extending the capabilities of the existing “writer” class within the hls4ml framework, we crafted a suite of new functions encapsulated under the “writer_IP” designation. This suite functions harmoniously with the existing codebase, allowing users to transition from a conventional monolithic synthesis approach to our innovative parallel IP core structure without drastic changes to their workflow. The functions are:

- `def IP project(self, model, hls_model):` Going through the HLS model → writing and building a model for each layer .
- `def write IP project script(self, hls_model, locdir):` Writing a new tcl script for the projects
- `def write IP VIVADO HLS script(self, model, locdir):` Writing the tcl script for VIVADO HLS → creating RTL (IP) for each model.
- `def write IP VIVADO script(self, model, locdir):` Writing the tcl script for VIVADO → connecting each IP model.

The “writer_IP” runs the tcl scripts and by that creates the model ready for implementation on a Fpga.

The “writer_IP” facilitates a modular design where each neural network layer is synthesized as an independent IP core. These cores are then orchestrated to work in tandem, significantly optimizing the synthesis timeline. Despite this partitioned approach, the automated process ensures that the integrity of the neural network's functionality is maintained, with all IP cores working in unison to mirror the performance of a singular monolithic IP.

In summary, the results confirm that the new architecture not only achieves a significant reduction in synthesis time but also unexpectedly enhances the latency and power performance without compromising resource utilization. The successful automation within the hls4ml library paves the way for this approach to become a standard practice for rapid prototyping and deployment of neural networks on FPGAs within the LHC experiments and potentially other real-time data processing applications.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the project "Faster FPGA Firmware Synthesis with hls4ml" has successfully demonstrated that by re-architecting neural network implementations to utilize modular IP blocks, synthesis times can be significantly reduced without compromising on latency or resource utilization. Through a novel approach that harnesses the parallel synthesis capabilities of modern FPGAs, we have achieved synthesis time reductions of 2x to 20x, depending on the complexity of the neural network model.

The implications of this work are far-reaching for the high-energy physics community, especially for the LHC experiments that operate under stringent latency constraints. The enhanced speed of prototyping and flexibility provided by the developed methodology facilitates the swift deployment of complex machine learning algorithms, thereby potentially accelerating scientific discoveries.

Moreover, the minor latency and power reduction observed as a collateral benefit of the modular design underscores the importance of architectural considerations in digital design. While the project focused on sequential neural network models, the principles laid out in this study lay a foundation for expanding to more complex network architectures.

This work also underscores the significance of making sophisticated FPGA programming accessible to researchers with limited hardware programming expertise. The extension of the hls4ml library to include the "writer_IP" classes functions enable a broader segment of the scientific community to leverage FPGA technology for machine learning applications.

Ultimately, this project exemplifies how thoughtful engineering and software design can dramatically improve hardware utilization in high-performance environments, setting a new benchmark for efficient FPGA firmware synthesis in the realm of machine learning. The achievements of this project pave the way for several exciting avenues of future research and development in the field of FPGA firmware synthesis for machine learning applications. The current methodology is optimized for sequential neural network models. Future work could extend the modular synthesis approach to accommodate complex architectures such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and more.

6. REFERENCES

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